

Innocence and Independence: Daisy Miller as an Archetype of the 19th-Century American Woman

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Article Info

Received: 09.09.2025
Accepted: 23.09.2025
Published: 30.09.2025

Keywords:
DaisyMiller,
Innocence,
Societal expectations,
Cultural contrasts.

ABSTRACT

Daisy Miller by Henry James uses the tragic story of a young American woman to examine the moral and cultural conflicts between European aristocratic customs and American individuality. The novella, which is mostly read from Frederick Winterbourne's limited and subjective point of view, focuses on Daisy's misinterpreted actions and eventual alienation. Daisy's ambiguity is highlighted by this narrative technique, which makes her both apparent and invisible. Deeper concerns about gender, class, and cultural identity in a transatlantic setting are revealed by the text's main question: Is Daisy a socially disruptive character or simply a witness to misconceptions?

This essay argues that Daisy symbolizes American uniqueness because of her refusal to follow social standards and her insistence on personal autonomy. But the European elite's severe moral criticism and patriarchal assessment of her show how damaging strict social norms can be. In the end, Daisy's conflicted portrayal forces readers to reevaluate popular ideas about morality, rebellion, and womanhood at the intersection of two contrasting cultures.

Masumiyet ve Bağımsızlık: Daisy Miller'in 19. Yüzyıl Amerikan Kadını Arketipi Olarak Temsili

Article Info

Received: 09.09.2025
Accepted: 23.09.2025
Published: 30.09.2025

Keywords:
Sensory dissolution,
Inter-painting,
Perception,
Contemporary Art.

TURKISH ABSTRACT

Henry James'in Daisy Miller adlı eseri, genç bir Amerikalı kadının trajik hikâyesi aracılığıyla Avrupa aristokrat gelenekleri ile Amerikan bireyciliği arasındaki ahlaki ve kültürel çatışmaları inceler.

Genellikle Frederick Winterbourne'un sınırlı ve öznel bakış açısından aktarılan bu novella, Daisy'nin yanlış anlaşılabilir davranışlarına ve nihai toplumsal dışlanışına odaklanır. Anlatı tekniği, Daisy'yi hem görünür hem de görünmez kılarak onun belirsizliğini ön plana çıkarır. Metnin temel sorusu; Daisy toplumsal düzeni bozan bir karakter midir yoksa yalnızca yanlış anlamaların kurbanı mıdır? Eser cinsiyet, sınıf ve kültürel kimlik gibi daha derin meseleleri gündeme getirir.

Bu makale, Daisy'nin toplumsal normlara uymayı reddetmesi ve kişisel özerklik konusundaki ısrarı sayesinde Amerikan özgünlüğünün bir simgesi hâline geldiğini öne sürer.

Ancak Avrupa elitinin ona yönelttiği sert ahlaki eleştiriler ve ataerkil yargılar, katı

toplumsal normların ne denli yıkıcı olabileceğini gözler önüne serer. Sonuç olarak, Daisy'nin çelişkili şekilde tasvir edilmesi, okuyucuyu iki farklı kültürün kesişiminde ahlak, isyan ve kadınlık kavramlarını yeniden değerlendirmeye zorlar.

Atf: Yılmaz, H., S. (2025). Innocence and Independence: Daisy Miller as an Archetype of the 19th-Century American Woman. *Musartia Journal*, 1(1), 51-56. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17206568>

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Introduction

The nineteenth century was a period in which the United States sought to construct its own cultural identity in contrast to Europe. During this process, literature became a significant medium for defining the national character and for discussing the role of women in society. The fate of the American woman was often associated, on the one hand, with democratic and individualistic values and the ideal of emancipation, and on the other hand, with constant comparison to Europe's established traditions and rigid social norms.

Henry James's *Daisy Miller*, first published in 1878, is one of the most striking texts in which these oppositions and cultural tensions are explored. The novella presents the position of the young American woman Daisy Miller within European society, focusing on her oscillation between innocence and independence. Daisy's actions are frequently misinterpreted by European observers and judged as violations of social decorum. These misunderstandings not only highlight the challenges faced by an individual woman but also question the emerging values of America itself.

The work is remarkable for its depiction of how innocence and the pursuit of freedom are shaped in the face of social expectations and patriarchal judgments. Through the character of Daisy, James opens a discussion on the boundaries of both individual identity and cultural belonging. In this sense, *Daisy Miller* is not merely a love story or a tale of social ostracism but also a symbolic representation of the clash of values between two cultures.

The purpose of this study is to examine how the character of Daisy in Henry James's *Daisy Miller* is positioned as an archetype of the nineteenth-century American woman within the axis of innocence and individual freedom. In this study, Daisy Miller's search for innocence and independence will be analyzed as a literary construction of the archetypal nineteenth-century American woman, while the cultural conflict between European and American norms will be examined from a gender perspective.

Methodology

This study adopts a qualitative research approach based on close reading and textual analysis. The primary source of the research is Henry James's novella *Daisy Miller* (1878), which is examined in the light of

cultural and gender studies. Secondary sources include scholarly articles, critical essays, and literary analyses that contextualize the novella.

Innocent and Independent American Woman: Daisy Miller

Daisy Miller is a novella written by Henry James in 1878. The novella is a mixture of melodrama and romance. Yet it ends with an irony that Henry James wants to express to his readers. This novella introduces a young American woman who represents the conflicts between American individualism and European aristocratic values. Daisy Miller, with her independent spirit, naivety, and resistance to societal expectations, represents the archetype of the American woman in the late 19th century. Throughout the late 19th century, American women were increasingly caught between the traditional ideals of femininity (innocence, piety, and domesticity) and the new opportunities for personal freedom and self-expression. The archetype of the American woman, therefore, can be seen as a symbol of both innocence and rebellion. Many literary and historical figures from this era reflect this duality. While some women embraced the innocence associated with domestic life, others, particularly those who engaged in the suffrage movement or took on careers outside the home, rejected these conventions, pushing back against the constraints of traditional femininity. This rebellion, often portrayed as naive or innocent in itself, became a key theme in the development of the American woman's archetype. Daisy Miller's interactions with the expatriate community in Europe and her rejection of traditional social codes reveal deep cultural conflicts. Daisy shows a greater degree of independence than any previous female Winterbourne has encountered. Her refusal to listen to the suggestions of others, even males, reflects her American upbringing and her inherently obstinate character. She independently makes her own decisions, even when they are unwise:

'I have never allowed a gentleman to dictate to me, or to interfere with anything I do.' (James, 2005, p. 40).

In this essay, Daisy Miller's innocence, individualism, and her clash with European norms will be explored to argue that she serves as both a symbol of American femininity and a critique of societal constraints on freedom and self-expression.

The novella arises from the simple circumstances. An American girl of the 1870s who has no more experience of the world than she got in her native town goes to Europe with her mother and her brother. The novella is a love story of Daisy Miller and Frederick Winterbourne. At the same time, set in Switzerland and in Rome, *Daisy Miller* reflects romanticism with the setting of Switzerland and life of high society with the setting of Rome. James portrays Daisy as 'an idealistic and intelligent girl, not the flirtatious hunting for a husband type' (Koy, 2010, p. 19).

In *Daisy Miller* Henry James uses focalizer, which makes the readers' perception of Daisy subjective. It means James focuses on the interior world of Winterbourne's mind and tries to portray the inside of the mind. 'All characters discuss her and evaluate her behavior all the time, but the reader is never offered direct access to her consciousness and motives' (Izzo, 2001, p. 23) The reader evaluates Daisy's behaviours or makes a judgement about her through the Winterbourne's consciousness and she is framed by patriarchal norms. For instance, when Daisy asks Winterbourne's opinion about Mrs Walker's criticism, the narrator tells the subjective truth:

'Does Mr. Winterbourne think, she asked slowly, smiling, throwing back her head, and glancing at him from head to foot, 'that, to save my reputation, I ought to get into the carriage?' Winterbourne colored; for an instant he hesitated greatly. It seemed so strange to hear her speak that way of her reputation. But he himself, in fact, must speak in accordance with gallantry. The finest gallantry, here, was simply to tell her the truth; and the truth, for Winterbourne, as the few indications I have been able to give have made him known to the reader, was that Daisy Miller should take Mrs. Walker's advice. He looked at her exquisite prettiness, and then he said, very gently, 'I think you should get into the carriage' (James, 2005, p. 61).

Mrs. Costello also finds herself offended by Daisy's excessive familiarity with male companions; nevertheless, she takes into account the societal constraints imposed on women in contrast to men. Her comment to Winterbourne regarding men's freedom to associate with whoever they choose is a reality she herself finds distasteful.

'Of course, a man may know every one. Men are welcome to the privilege!' (James, 2005, p. 32).

That's why, 'to prove Daisy a dangerous and predatory American female is difficult because all the evidence for or against her, of course, comes to the reader at second hand, some of it hearsay. In addition, those characters who speak or act against Daisy, like Mrs Costello or Mrs. Walker, are portrayed as distinctly unpleasant snobs' (Kirk, 1993, p. 277). At first, it is possible to think Daisy as a girl who selfishly attempts to use Winterbourne to satisfy her social and psychological needs. Yet, "characteristics such as the appealing syntax of Daisy's speech, the blushes that reveal her hidden feelings, and the twisting of her parasol and fan play off a stereotype but are made so particular to Daisy that in another setting they would seem but imitation of her" (Haralson & Johnson, 2009, pp. 222-223). The true nature of Daisy's character leads her to death. 'Daisy as a naive girl, neglected by her family, left to carve her own way through European society, and finally cruelly sacrificed by expatriated snobs with misogynistic double standards' (Haralson & Johnson, 2009, p. 222) moves her slowly out of society and is alienated. Because she has a free spirit and she does whatever she wants by ignoring moral values of European aristocracy and social norms to which they live. Daisy's innocence is symbolic one to indicates parameters of the society. 'Daisy knows no evil and is unable

to think it; she cannot comprehend why her behaviour, which seems harmless enough to her, should be the cause of so much social anxiety' (Koy, 2010, p. 14). On the other hand, in the eyes of society she is a vulgar and a flirtatious woman who does not care moral and social values. 'The protagonist is never presented from her own point of view, and her inner perceptions are never brought into focus. She is central and omnipresent because she represents the enigma at the center of the interpretative efforts of the others' (Izzo, 2001, p. 245).

From the beginning to the end, Winterbourne's prejudice prevents him from the realization of Daisy's love and nature until she dies. 'Winterbourne's treatment of Daisy has been variously interpreted as illustrative of patriarchal society, the double standards of gender roles, and class snobbery. His treatment of her has also been seen to symbolize the relationship of fiction to life. Daisy becomes a symbolic character who remains ultimately ambiguous' (Izzo, 2001, p. 273). People's blindness gives her behaviours a very different meaning. Actually, what looks different in the eyes of European is remarkably self-reliant American heroine's free spirit.

With realist representation, Daisy is the prototype of young American girls encountering Europe. She represents American adolescent girls who are reluctant to submit to the beginning the adult womanhood that is perceived as breaking the will of society. Daisy tries to escape from the ambivalence about the dependence of her private self and her public appearance by going against Mrs Costello, who questions Daisy's virtue and Mrs Walker, who tries to shape Daisy's behaviours to the values of her society. Besides, "Daisy Miller's behavior exhibits either the self-determination of the flirt or the illusory nature of her mastery" (Wardley, 1991, pp. 232-254). She is dismissive and she refuses to take any advice seriously, and insists on her right to do what she pleases regardless of the opinions of others.

'I have never allowed a gentleman to dictate to me, or to interfere with anything I do' (James, 2005, p. 57).

Winterbourne supposes that Daisy's behaviours and activities are so clear and easy to understand. That is the reason why he cannot solve his dilemma and decide whether she is innocent or not. 'His failure to understand the –'new' American girl, represented by Daisy, in the end only accentuates her sense of isolation; in Europe, the transplanted American Daisy can only wither and die' (Koy, 2010, p. 14). James supports Daisy's innocence and Winterbourne's misinterpretation of Daisy's behavior with Giovanelli's final confession:

'She was the most beautiful young lady I ever saw, and the most amiable'; and then he added in a moment, 'and she was the most innocent.' (James, 2005, p. 87).

Although the different social codes which restrict Daisy's character, Daisy is a free woman who shapes her life by herself. James emphasizes Daisy's activities in the middle of the story rather than her untimely end. Daisy as a free woman controls her life and is an admirable figure who makes her own decisions. So, Daisy's innocence or in other words her resistance can be accepted as a virtue or as a willful ignorance.

The European community's hatred for her lifestyle alienates her, and her tragic demise serves as a critique of the severity of social judgment and the constrained opportunities for women's autonomy under conventional societal frameworks. Her rejection of traditional norms results in her death, which is portrayed as punishment for her independence and innocence.

In conclusion, Daisy Miller represents a new kind of American woman: innocent yet assertive, misunderstood yet honest. Through her fate, Henry James critiques the rigidity of European social norms and the cost of individuality in a patriarchal world.

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